

Digital Literacy on Mathematical Performance of College Students in the Course Mathematics in the Modern World

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ABSTRACT

The increasing reliance on digital technologies for learning and problem-solving is crucial to understanding how digital literacy skills affect students' performance in mathematics. The research explored the relationship between digital literacy levels and mathematical performance through a quantitative analysis of data collected from college students enrolled in the course Mathematics in the Modern World during the Academic Year 2022-2023. This research investigates the relationship between students' ability to effectively use digital tools and their academic achievement in mathematical subjects. This study found that the student has a very satisfactory (91.82%) performance in the course Mathematics in the Modern World. However, students' digital literacy skills need further improvement and support. The study highlights the importance of fostering digital literacy skills among students and the need for ongoing efforts to improve digital literacy levels. It also suggests that digital literacy may not directly impact mathematical performance, and other variables may have a more significant impact. Additionally, the study indicates that the course could reassess the importance placed on digital literacy and that more research is needed to understand the relationship between digital literacy and mathematical performance.

Subject Area

Mathematics Education

Keywords: *Digital Literacy; Mathematical Performance; Mathematics in the Modern World; Mathematics Education*

INTRODUCTION

Technology has progressed throughout the twenty-first century and has developed an avenue for easy access to information and resources for learning (Raja & Nagasubramani, 2018). Implementing technology in education is a practice that has been introduced previously in the academe. As technology progresses, education adapts to these changes and incorporates them to improve the quality of learning further. During the pandemic, the Philippines has implemented online distance learning, encouraging students to use educational devices to continue learning (Toquero, 2020). Furthermore, the use of these devices continues in the post-pandemic and works in tandem with face-to-face classes.

The way students learn in modern times has changed significantly. Students are well-suited to technological advancements and are considered technological natives in the digital era (Dingli & Setchell, 2015). Digital literacy is using digital technologies effectively and efficiently to access, evaluate, and use information for a specific purpose. It includes using and navigating digital devices, software, and online platforms and critically analyzing and evaluating online content for accuracy and reliability. Digital literacy also involves understanding digital privacy and security issues and using digital technologies safely and ethically (Atoy et al., 2020; Baterna et al., 2020).

Technology is just a tool, so it is crucial to use diverse approaches and strategies to help students explore and understand mathematical concepts. The use of technology is ongoing and has many possibilities that enhance student learning in math. Students learn mathematics in a multitude of ways with the use of technology. Through interactive games and visual aids, technology can provide students with hands-on, interactive games and tools that help them learn mathematical concepts better. Tools like the Geometer's Sketchpad, MathBlaster, Mathletics, or Khan Academy have interactive games and visual aids to help students better understand concepts, formulas, and algorithms (Drijvers, 2015; Hwa, 2018). Moreover, gamification and personalization, where platforms and software try to engage students with "gamification" techniques, can facilitate learning as students stay motivated to play educational games. In addition, technology education software often adapts the learning experience to individual student needs so that each student can learn at a personalized pace (Turan et al., 2016).

The increasing use of technology in modern classrooms has raised concerns about how it affects students' mathematical performance. Digital literacy skills are becoming more crucial in today's society, and students need to be equipped with them to succeed in the modern workforce. By researching the relationship between digital literacy and math performance, educators and policymakers can work to ensure that all students have access to the resources they need to succeed and investigate the impact of digital literacy on the math performance of the students (McCulloch et al., 2018).

The knowledge gap between mathematical performance and technological literacy refers to the discrepancy between a person's mathematical abilities and technological proficiency. This gap has become more significant due to the increasing reliance on technology in academic and professional environments. While individuals may have strong mathematical skills, they may need more technical knowledge to apply them effectively in a digital setting. It is also essential to provide students with a strong foundation in mathematical principles and problem-solving skills while

teaching them the specific technical skills they need to apply them in a digital environment (Pagani et al., 2016; Chetty et al., 2018).

The study assesses the association between the student's mathematical performance and digital literacy. Consequently, it would determine the relationship between variables and provide information for modifying existing teaching methodologies to help teachers' and students' overall learning experience. It would also investigate how digital literacy affects students' math performance to help develop more targeted curricula.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The study is grounded in Hannafin and Land's (1997) theory of technology-based student-centered learning, serving as the principal foundation for investigating the elements of students' technology-assisted learning. The study also anchors on McLean, Oldfield, and Stephen's (2020) work on the Digital Literacy Skills Framework that helps assess the students' digital literacy.

The study's conceptual framework is displayed in Figure 1, illustrating the correlation design. The independent variable is the students' digital literacy, and the dependent variable is the mathematical performance. The study used the four levels of digital literacy to categorize learners' proficiency levels using technology and online resources.

Figure 1.
Schematic diagram of the study

Technological advancement characterizes the twenty-first century. Technology is integral to many people's lives as it makes work easier and faster. Moreover, technological influence extends to the field of education and impacts the overall learning process (Raja & Nagasubramani, 2018). The tertiary education system in the Philippines continues to use the technologies implemented during the pandemic. Many educational institutions modified their learning modalities to incorporate technology in all aspects of learning (Toquero, 2020).

According to Raja and Nagasubrami (2018), with access to the internet, digital literacy enables students to access various online resources that could aid their mathematical learning. They can use online calculators, graphing tools, videos, and simulations to understand mathematical concepts better. Moreover, according to Bernacki, Greene, and Crompton (2020), digital literacy can help students develop better problem-solving skills by using online forums and discussion boards to collaborate with other students and teachers.

With digital literacy, students can use advanced software and computer programs to perform complex mathematical calculations quickly and accurately. Technology saves time and minimizes errors when working with large amounts of data. Additionally, digital literacy can help students learn through visualization. Many online tools and software can create graphics and visual

representations of mathematical concepts to help students understand better (Reddy et al., 2020). According to PowerSchool (2021), digital literacy is becoming increasingly critical with the growing importance of technology in every field. Thus, students who learn math with digital tools will be better prepared for the digital future.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The primary purpose of this study is to assess the association between the students' mathematical performance in the course Mathematics in the Modern World and digital literacy.

Specifically, the study sought to answer the following problems:

1. What is the level of students' academic performance in Mathematics in the Modern World?
2. What is the level of students' digital literacy?
3. Is there a significant difference on the students' mathematics performance when considering the student digital literacy?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the students' mathematical performance and digital literacy?

METHODOLOGY

The study employed a descriptive correlational design (Creswell & Creswell, 2017). The target respondents of this study are the students taking the course on Mathematics in the Modern World at San Isidro College (SIC) course during the Academic Year 2022-2023. In this study, the researcher used an achievement test on content and the digital literacy questionnaire (DLQ). A face-to-face examination collected data for the achievement test, and Google Forms facilitated the administration of the DLQ. The students had one week to complete the DLQ form.

The content-validated achievement test contained 40 multiple choice questions with twenty (20) questions per topic discussed: 1) logic and 2) statistics. To determine the validity of the test items, the researcher ensured that the questionnaire had undergone a content and structure review by three (3) experts. The interpretation of the result of the student's mathematical exam scores used the scale below, as adopted from the grading system of San Isidro College after the transmutation of the scores;

<u>Range Scale</u>	<u>Level of Achievement</u>	<u>Qualitative Interpretation</u>
96% – 100%	Exemplary	Excellent
93% – 95%	Outstanding	Superior
87% – 92%	Above Average	Very Satisfactory
81% – 86%	Average	Satisfactory
78% – 80%	Fair	Good
75% – 77%	Below Average	Fair
74% and Below	Deficient	Did Not Meet Expectation

The primary instrument of this study adopted the questionnaire developed by Papas Education (2020) that is anchored on the work of McLean, Oldfield, and Stephens (2020) on digital literacy, with twenty (20) statements following the Digital Literacy Skills Framework. The digital literacy questionnaire (DLQ) follows the 4-point scale where the students evaluate themselves on digital

literacy. The questionnaire has a Cronbach-Alpha of 0.737. The criteria developed by McLean, Oldfield, and Stephens (2020) follow the range:

<u>Scale</u>	<u>Range</u>	<u>Qualitative Interpretation</u>
4	3.26 – 4.00	<i>Digital Literacy Level 3</i>
3	2.51 – 3.25	<i>Digital Literacy Level 2</i>
2	1.76 – 2.50	<i>Digital Literacy Level 1</i>
1	1.00 – 1.75	<i>Digital Literacy Pre-Level 1</i>

Adhering to data privacy, the researcher asked permission from the students to use the data they provided. Once the students signed the consent, this signified the student's acceptance and willingness to participate in the study. Using statistical software, the researcher organized and encoded data from the achievement test and DLQ—the data treatment utilized descriptive statistics, specifically the mean and standard deviation. The ANOVA test compared the students' mathematical performance with their digital literacy level. Moreover, the researcher used the Pearson-moment correlation to establish the relationship between students' academic performance and digital literacy level.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The study ascertained the relationship between mathematical performance and digital literacy of college students taking a Mathematics course in the Modern World. The study gathered data for mathematical performance through teacher records and digital literacy through surveys. Additionally, the study used descriptive statistics, ANOVA to compare the student's digital literacy considering their mathematical performance, and Person-moment correlation r to establish the relationship between the variables.

Students' Academic Performance in Mathematics in the Modern World

Table 1 presents the mathematical performance of college students in Mathematics in the Modern World. Additionally, Table 1 presents the percentage of the student's performance with the qualitative interpretation.

Table 1.

Students' academic performance in Mathematics in the Modern World.

Variable	Performance	Qualitative Interpretation
Mathematical Performance	91.82%	Very Satisfactory

As shown in Table 1, the overall performance of the students in the course was very satisfactory. The result suggests that the students have successfully grasped the concepts and skills taught in the course. The students have performed well in assessments, coursework, and class participation, indicating a high level of comprehension and application of mathematical principles. The result implies that the students have demonstrated a strong understanding and competence in the subject matter (Guinocor et al., 2020).

Furthermore, these results convey that most students have met or exceeded the expectations set for the course. The result suggests that the course content is appropriately challenging and adequately prepares students to apply mathematical concepts in real-world scenarios (Roman & Villanueva, 2019; Ellvan & Edig, 2022). The 91.82% performance rating indicates a positive

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outcome, reflecting students' solid mathematical performance and a successful teaching-learning process in Mathematics in the Modern World (Cornillez et al., 2020).

Students' Level of Students' Digital Literacy

Table 2 presents the students' digital literacy level with the frequency and percentage per level.

Table 2.

Students' digital literacy according to level.

Variable	<i>f</i>	%
Digital Literacy Level 3	4	7.14
Digital Literacy Level 2	28	50.00
Digital Literacy Level 1	22	39.29
Digital Literacy Pre-Level 1	2	3.57
TOTAL	56	100

The results, as presented in Table 2, show that the students have a relatively low level of digital literacy. The result indicates that 39.29% of students have a digital literacy level 1 and 3.57% have a digital literacy pre-level 1. A significant portion of the student population needs a higher digital literacy level. The result is evidenced by the fact that 39.29% of the students possess a digital literacy level 1, and 3.57% have digital literacy pre-level 1. The result suggests that there may be a need for further initiatives or programs to improve digital literacy skills among students (Baterna et al., 2020). Additionally, the relatively small percentage (7.14%) of students at level 3 implies that a relatively small proportion of students possess advanced digital literacy skills (Chetty et al., 2018; Purnamasari et al., 2021).

Moreover, there is a difference in the number of digital literacy levels among students. The result can be seen from the increasing percentages as we move from pre-level 1 to level 3. Furthermore, it is essential to note that a considerable number of students (50%) have a digital literacy level 2. The result suggests that a moderate level of digital literacy exists among a significant portion of the student population.

Table 3 presents the overall digital literacy of college students taking a Mathematics in the Modern World course with the mean and qualitative interpretation.

Table 3.

Students' level of digital literacy.

Variable	Mean	Qualitative Interpretation
Digital Literacy	2.61	Level 2

As presented in Table 3, the result implies that they have a basic understanding of digital tools and technologies. However, their skills might be limited, or they may need to be fully proficient in using them (Atoy et al., 2020; Udeogalanya, 2022). The result suggests that the students have some fundamental digital literacy knowledge but may need help with more advanced tasks or technology in more complex ways (Marci-Boehncke & Vogel, 2018; Tohara, 2021). They may require further development and training to enhance their digital skills (Baterna et al., 2020).

Students' Mathematical Performance Considering the Students' Digital Literacy

Table 4 presents the comparison of the mathematical performance of the college students in the course Mathematics in the Modern World when grouped according to their digital literacy level.

Table 4.

Students mathematical performance when grouped according to digital literacy level.

Level	Mean	Std. Dev.	<i>f</i>	<i>p</i>
Level 3	94.15 a	2.873		
Level 2	91.51 a	6.331		
Level 1	90.45 a	4.571	0.694	0.560
Pre-Level 1	88.75 a	1.747		

Table 4 presents the f-value of the four (4) levels as 0.694 with a p-value of 0.560 ($p > 0.05$), indicating that there is no significant difference between the mathematical performance of the students when grouped according to their digital literacy level. The results suggest that digital literacy does not significantly impact mathematical performance. The result means that students with different levels of digital literacy perform equally well in mathematics.

As presented in Table 4, digital literacy may be a minor factor in determining mathematical abilities. The result suggests that good digital skills do not automatically translate into better mathematical abilities. Digital literacy may be a separate skill set that does not strongly correlate with math performance (Tatar et al., 2015). However, while there may not be a direct relationship between digital literacy and math performance, it is possible that digital skills indirectly contribute to mathematical success in other ways (Agustin & Winarso, 2021). Students with higher digital literacy may have better access to online resources or utilize digital tools that enhance their learning experience, leading to comparable math performance (Dofková, 2016; Purnamasari et al., 2021).

Students with different digital literacy levels may be compensating through other means; i.e., the students with varying digital literacy levels are performing similarly in math; it could suggest that those with lower digital skills are compensating for their weakness through other strategies or resources (Busnawir et al., 2023). These students may be relying on traditional learning methods or other non-digital resources to succeed in mathematics (Maracci et al., 2023).

Relationship between Mathematical Performance and Students' Digital Literacy

Table 5 presents the association between the students' mathematical performance in Mathematics in the Modern World and digital literacy.

Table 5.

Association between Students' Mathematical Performance and Digital Literacy.

Variable	Mean	<i>r</i>	Extent of Relationship	<i>p</i>
Mathematical Performance	91.19			
Digital Literacy	2.61	0.187	Negligible Correlation	0.167

The results presented in Table 5 show a correlation value of 0.187, indicating no significant relationship between the student's mathematical performance and digital literacy. The absence of

a relationship suggests no meaningful connection between mathematical performance and digital literacy (Agustin & Winarso, 2021). The result indicates that the students' competency in using digital technologies does not necessarily predict their ability in mathematics (Leoste et al., 2022), which Table 4 further supports.

Moreover, the ability to navigate and utilize digital technologies does not significantly impact their mathematical skills or vice versa (Pagani et al., 2016). Furthermore, a negligible correlation between mathematical performance and digital literacy suggests that these skills may exist independently. Additional factors could be considered when addressing proficiency in either domain (Tatar et al., 2015).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Based on the study's results, the teaching methodology, materials, and overall effectiveness of the course have contributed to the student's success in Mathematics in the Modern World. While the students possess some level of digital literacy, there is a need for further improvement and support to raise their proficiency to higher levels. This could involve providing additional resources, training, or educational programs focused on developing the students' digital literacy skills. Generally, the results highlight the importance of fostering digital literacy skills among students and the need for ongoing efforts to improve digital literacy levels across the board.

Moreover, the digital literacy level does not predict mathematical performance in Mathematics in the Modern World. The emphasis on digital literacy may not improve mathematical skills directly. Other variables, such as previous mathematics education, teaching quality, or individual learning abilities, could have a more significant impact on mathematical performance. In this study, digital literacy may not be the dominant factor affecting students' mathematical performance. Likewise, the course may need to reassess the importance placed on digital literacy in mathematical performance and curriculum design. The lack of significant difference in mathematical performance could also be due to small sample sizes. It is essential to acknowledge and consider these factors before drawing firm conclusions. Overall, the absence of a significant difference in mathematical performance grouped by digital literacy level suggests that more research is warranted to understand the complex relationship between digital literacy and math achievement.

Furthermore, the lack of correlation indicates that being good at mathematics does not necessarily mean being proficient in digital literacy, and vice versa. These skills are separate skills that can be developed and improved independently. The result highlights the need for a balanced education that includes developing mathematical skills and digital literacy to prepare individuals for various aspects of their personal and professional lives.

The study recommends the following: (1) The course can incorporate digital literacy components into mathematics lessons to help students understand how to use technology to enhance their mathematical skills, such as utilizing online calculators, graphing tools, or programming languages for problem-solving. (2) encourage students to work on interdisciplinary projects combining mathematical concepts with digital tools or technology-driven problem-solving that would help enhance their mathematical proficiency and digital literacy simultaneously. And (3) acknowledge the independence of mathematical performance and digital

literacy, emphasizing the importance of a well-rounded education that includes these domains to prepare students for the demands of an increasingly digitized society.

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